

RECONMATIC

Brand Guidelines

Welcome to RECONMATIC brand book

This brand book contains the fundamentals of RECONMATIC positioning. It has been created to reflect our approach and to drive awareness around the organisation. In the following pages, you will find information on how to apply the visual identity consistently, effectively and efficiently.

The principles of our communication

The RECONMATIC brand identity is the tangible expression of what we stand for. RECONMATIC is an EU project funded by the #HorizonEurope Research & Innovation Action programme, that proposes a suite of innovative tools & techniques to build bridges through "bottom-up" construction and demolition waste (CDW) prevention and handling to reach "top-down" European waste reduction goals. Eco friendly approach to life, sustainability, recycling and upcycling, green technology, construction and waste management are the core values the RECONMATIC project represents.

Brand Elements

LOGOTYPE

Logotype anatomy

icon

Reconmatic

wordmark

Color negative logotype

Logotype on dark background

Color usage | Alternative colors

Version on white

Version on black

Clearspace and minimum size

Exclusion zone (clearspace)

The logo's and icon's exclusion zones are equal to the height of the wordmark's capital letter

Minimum print size

40mm

Minimum digital size

90px

Incorrect use

Always protect the integrity and appearance of our logotype. No modification or reinterpretation of the logo should occur as per the illustrated examples.

DO NOT use colors on logo that are not approved

DO NOT blend or add any drop shadow effect on logo

DO NOT stretch logo in any way

DO NOT flip any part of logo horizontally or vertically

DO NOT create outline borders around logo or outline logo

DO NOT change position or size of any part of logo

Brand Elements

THE COLORS

Color palette

C 27
M 0
Y 91
K 0

R 197
G 255
B 76

C 58
M 0
Y 87
K 0

R 56
G 247
B 105

C 70
M 0
Y 91
K 0

R 0
G 207
B 85

Color palette

C 0
M 0
Y 0
K 100

R 0
G 0
B 0

C 4
M 3
Y 3
K 0

R 242
G 242
B 242

Color scheme

Why are we using these colors?

- Tech, recycling industries and accessibility
- The horizon of a greener future to inspire and engage
- Reduction of the impact construction waste has on the environment

Logo use against backgrounds

DO'S

DON'TS

Brand Elements

THE TYPOGRAPHY

The typography

Typeface for print media

Trebuchet MS will be used for print media communications.

Trebuchet MS is a humanist sans-serif typeface that Vincent Connare designed for Microsoft Corporation in 1996. Trebuchet MS was the font used for the window titles in the Windows XP default theme, succeeding MS Sans Serif and Tahoma.

It is available for download:

<https://www.cufonfonts.com/font/trebuchet-ms-2>

Aa

Trebuchet MS Regular
Trebuchet MS Italic
Trebuchet MS Bold
Trebuchet MS Bold Italic

Trebuchet MS

A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X
Y Z 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0 ! @ # \$ % ^ & * ()

The typography

Typeface for online use

Ubuntu will be used for online communications.

Ubuntu is a sans-serif typeface by Dalton Maag, uses OpenType features and is manually hinted for clarity on desktop and mobile computing screens. The scope of the Ubuntu Font Family includes all the languages used by the various Ubuntu users around the world in tune with Ubuntu's philosophy which states that every user should be able to use their software in the language of their choice.

It is available for download:

<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Ubuntu>

Aa

Ubuntu

Ubuntu Light

Ubuntu Light Italic

Ubuntu Regular

Ubuntu Italic

Ubuntu Medium

Ubuntu Medium Italic

Ubuntu Bold

Ubuntu Bold Italic

A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X
Y Z 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 0 ! @ # \$ % ^ & * ()

Stationary

Letterhead

Font used: Trebuchet MS

THANK YOU
FOR YOUR ATTENTION